

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

TITLE OF STUDY: Eco-Guilt and Eco-Responsibility in Solid Waste Management Practices: Evidence from a Philippine Local Community

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR/S:

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INTRODUCTION

You are being asked to take part in a research study. Before you decide to participate, you must understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully. Kindly ask the researcher if anything needs to be clarified or if you need more information.

PURPOSE OF STUDY

I am a faculty researcher from the University of Rizal System, Rodriguez, researching Eco-Guilt and Eco-Responsibility in Solid Waste Management Practices: Evidence from a Philippine Local Community.

I will give you information and invite you to participate in this research. You do not have to decide today whether or not you will participate. Before you decide, talk to anyone you feel comfortable with about the research. With your knowledge and expertise, you can help me elaborate on the topic under study.

TYPE OF RESEARCH INTERVENTION

This research will involve your participation in a discussion that will take about 60-90 minutes of the interview.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary. It is your choice whether to participate or not. If you choose not to participate, the researcher will understand. If you participate, you may change your mind later and stop participating even if you agreed earlier.

PROCEDURES

1. The researcher will explain the concepts of the interview, including its purpose and procedures.
2. The researcher will remind you to express your willingness to participate.
3. The researcher will ask if it is convenient for you to record and take pictures of the interview process.
4. The researcher will confirm that you have received, read, and signed the informed consent form.
5. You will be asked to introduce yourself.

6. You will be told about the duration of the interview.
7. You will be asked about your ideas and experiences as part of the household practicing solid waste management.
8. You can use the Filipino/English language, whichever you prefer.
9. You might be chosen to participate in the member checking after the results are analyzed.

RISKS

You may decline to answer any or all questions and terminate your involvement at any time if you choose. You may share some personal or confidential information by chance, or you may feel uncomfortable talking about some of the topics. However, I do not wish for this to happen. You do not have to answer any questions or participate in the discussion if you feel the question (s) are too personal or if talking about them makes you uncomfortable.

BENEFITS

There will be no direct benefit to you, but your participation will help me find out more about the topic under study.

CONFIDENTIALITY

For this research study, your comments will be confidential. The researcher will make every effort to preserve your confidentiality, including the following:

- Assigning code names/numbers for participants that will be used on all research notes and documents.
- Keeping notes, interview transcriptions, and any other identifying participant information in a safe place in the personal possession of the researcher.
- Participant data will be kept confidential except in cases where the researcher is legally obligated to report specific incidents.
- Consent forms will be stored separately from transcripts and codes; digital files will be password-protected and accessible only to the study leader and collaborator/co-author.
- Direct quotations will be reviewed and anonymized before use to prevent identification of the participant, and context not relevant to the study.

CONTACT INFORMATION

Suppose you have questions at any time about this study, or you experience adverse effects as a result of participating in this study. In that case, you may contact the researcher whose contact information is provided on the first page.

CONSENT

I have read and understand the provided information and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I can withdraw at any time without giving a reason or cost. I understand that I will be given a copy of this consent form and the possibility of being chosen as a participant again in the member checking for results validation.

I voluntarily agree to participate in this research. Yes No

Participant's signature _____ Date _____

Investigator's signature _____ Date _____